

From Anxiety to Adaptation Examine the Coping Strategies Employed by Anxious Children

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This study investigates the coping strategies employed by anxious children aged 13 to 18 years of age in urban settings. The Sing the promise level 2 anxiety scale, and (CISS-21) data were collected from 50 randomly selected students to assess anxiety levels and corresponding coping mechanism finding reveals that 62% of participants experience moderate anxiety, while (22%) reported several levels. Problem solving emerged as the most preferred coping strategy (42%), with females predominantly using task-oriented methods and males showing a higher tendency toward avoiding. An age-related difference indicated that older adolescents demonstrated more adaptive coping skills. Statistical analyses confirmed a significant negative correlation between problem-focused coping and anxiety and a positive correlation between both avoidance and emotion-focused strategies with higher anxiety levels. This study highlights the important o early interventions, gender sensitive programs, and school-based mental health initiatives aimed at fostering adaptive coping and emotional resilience among adolescents.

Keywords: Anxiety, adolescent coping strategies, problem solving, avoidance, gender difference

Introduction

Background of the Study

Adolescence is a critical transitional stage characterized by rapid biological, emotional, cognitive, and social changes (Steinberg, 2014). During this period, young individuals are exposed to increased academic pressure, social expectations, identity exploration, and the need to develop autonomy, all of which can contribute to significant psychological stress (Arnett, 2015). In the absence of effective coping mechanisms, these challenges often manifest in the form of anxiety, which has emerged as one of the most prevalent mental health concerns among children and adolescents worldwide (World Health Organization [WHO], 2021).

In the Indian context, adolescent anxiety is further intensified by cultural, educational, and societal factors. A strong emphasis on academic excellence, highly competitive school environments, and changing family structures significantly influence anxiety levels among students (Deb, Strodl, & Sun, 2015; Verma & Sharma, 2017). Although a moderate degree of anxiety is considered a normal response to life stressors, persistent or elevated anxiety can adversely affect a child's emotional well-being, academic performance, and social functioning (American Psychiatric Association [APA], 2022).

Furthermore, many Indian families continue to hold traditional beliefs regarding discipline and mental health, often discouraging

open communication about emotional concerns. This creates barriers for adolescents in expressing distress or seeking psychological support (Kumar & Nehra, 2014). Cultural stigma surrounding mental health and high parental expectations frequently contribute to perfectionism, fear of failure, and emotional withdrawal among adolescents (Rao, 2019). Additional stressors such as peer comparison, body image concerns, and the pervasive influence of social media further exacerbate emotional turmoil and self-doubt during this developmental stage (Nesi, Choukas-Bradley, & Prinstein, 2018).

However substantial individual differences exist in how adolescent apply these cognitive strategies for example some may rely heavily on self-blame catastrophizing or repetitive negative thinking rumination all of which have been soon to contribute to poor psychological outcomes Garnefski et al. (2001) highlight that certain cognitive emotions regulation strategies particularly Mall adaptive ones like self-blame and catastrophizing are strongly link to emotional adjustment and increase vulnerability to anxiety and depression process the cognitive capacity emotional regulation the actual coping style they adopt are influenced by a combination of personal social and environmental factors.

Understanding these dynamics is essential for educator parents and mental health professionals aiming to support adolescent will be prompting adaptive coping and emotional regulation during this crucial development stage can significantly reduce the risk of long-term psychological difficulties and empower young individuals to face negative life challenges more effectively.

Statement of the Problem

Despite a growing body of global literature on childhood anxiety, there is a need for localized studies in Indian settings to explore how adolescents cope with anxiety. It is critical to identify which coping strategies are most commonly used by ancient children in urban School settings and how the strategies vary by gender and level of anxiety. This study aims to fill they fill this gap by examining the coping strategies employed by anxious children aged 13 to 18 using data from a sample of 50 students selected through random sampling.

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Review of Literature

Anxiety is a prevalent emotional disorder in children and adolescents, often emerging during early development stages and escalating under academic, familial, and social stress. The coping mechanisms adopted during adolescence have a profound effect on how individuals deal with stress in life. This paper presents a critical review of theories, concepts, and empirical findings relevant to anxiety and coping strategies among adolescents, with a special focus on Indian and global perspectives.

Theoretical Framework

Lazarus and Folkman's Stress and Coping Theory (1984)

Lazarus and Folkman explained coping as the way people try to handle stress when they feel that a situation is difficult or beyond their ability to manage. Coping includes the thoughts and actions a person uses to deal with stressful situations. It classifies coping into two broad types:

- Problem-focused coping refers to efforts made to solve the problem that is causing stress, such as finding solutions or taking action to change the situation.
- Emotion-focused coping refers to efforts made to control or reduce emotional stress, such as calming oneself or seeking emotional support.

Children use both types of coping strategies. The type of coping they use depends on their age, personality, and the kind of problem they are facing.

Cognitive Behavioral Theory of Anxiety

The cognitive behavioral theory of anxiety posits that maladaptive cognitions play a central role in the development and maintenance of anxiety disorders. According to this model, children and adolescents may develop distorted beliefs about themselves, others, and their environment, leading to heightened perceptions of threat and vulnerability (Beck & Clark, 1997). These cognitive distortions contribute to anxious emotions and avoidance behaviors. The theory further emphasizes that coping skills are learned and modifiable; through cognitive restructuring and behavioral interventions, individuals can replace negative thought patterns with more adaptive and realistic ones, thereby reducing anxiety and stress (Kendall, 2011).

Types of Anxiety in Children and Adolescents

The *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders* (DSM-5; American Psychiatric Association, 2013) identifies several anxiety disorders commonly observed in children and adolescents. These include:

- Generalized Anxiety Disorder, characterized by excessive and persistent worry across multiple domains
- Social Anxiety Disorder, involving intense fear of social situations and negative evaluation
- Separation Anxiety Disorder, marked by excessive fear related to separation from attachment figures
- Panic Disorder and Specific Phobias, involving sudden episodes of intense fear or irrational fears accompanied by physiological symptoms

Research indicates that adolescents often experience a

combination of academic and social anxieties, which may co-occur and intensify during this developmental phase (Beesdo et al., 2009).

Coping Strategies in Adolescence

Adaptive coping strategies promote psychological well-being and effective stress management. Common adaptive strategies among adolescents include seeking social support, problem-solving, planning, positive cognitive reframing, and engagement in physical activity or constructive hobbies. The use of these strategies has been consistently associated with lower anxiety levels, improved academic performance, and healthier social functioning (Compas et al., 2001).

Maladaptive Coping Strategies: Maladaptive coping strategies are often ineffective and may exacerbate psychological distress. These include avoidance, denial, substance use (particularly in late adolescence), aggression, and social withdrawal. Persistent reliance on maladaptive coping has been linked to chronic anxiety, depressive symptoms, and behavioral problems in adolescents (Essau et al., 2012).

Empirical Studies

Global research highlights developmental and gender-based differences in coping. Compas et al. (2001) reported that problem-focused coping becomes more prevalent with age, whereas younger children rely more heavily on emotion-focused strategies. Essau et al. (2012) found that adolescent girls tend to report higher anxiety levels and greater use of emotion-focused coping compared to boys. Kovacs and Staff (2001) demonstrated that higher cognitive flexibility is associated with more adaptive coping styles and reduced anxiety symptoms.

Indian Studies: Studies conducted in India emphasize the role of socio-cultural and academic pressures in shaping adolescent anxiety and coping. Kumar and Bhukar (2013) identified academic stress as a major predictor of anxiety among Indian adolescents. Sahoo et al. (2015) reported that many adolescents lack effective coping skills and often resort to avoidance and emotional suppression. Sahin et al. (2020) highlighted the protective role of family support and school-based counseling in fostering adaptive coping strategies.

Role of Family and School Environment

The family and school environments play a crucial role in the development of coping strategies during adolescence. Parental warmth, modeling of adaptive coping, open communication, and encouragement of autonomy contribute to healthier coping mechanisms. Similarly, supportive school climates, counseling services, emotional literacy programs, and peer support systems help adolescents manage stress more effectively (Rao, 2019).

Gender and Age Differences in Coping

Gender differences in coping are well documented. Girls are more likely to engage in emotional expression and rumination, whereas boys tend to use distraction or avoidance-based strategies (Hampel & Petermann, 2005). Age-related differences indicate that as adolescents mature, improvements in cognitive and emotional regulation lead to the adoption of more complex and adaptive coping strategies (Zimmer-Gembeck & Skinner, 2008).

The reviewed literature indicates that anxiety and coping during adolescence are multidimensional phenomena influenced by psychological, environmental, and demographic factors. Although

adolescents employ a wide range of coping strategies, their effectiveness depends on developmental stage, contextual demands, and available support systems. The review underscores a significant need for more empirical research within Indian urban school settings to better understand culturally specific coping patterns among adolescents.

Objectives of the Study

- To assess the level and types of anxiety among children aged 13 to 18 years.
- To identify the coping strategies employed by these anxious children.
- To explore any significant differences in coping strategies across age and gender.
- To provide recommendations for school-based mental health interventions.

Research Questions

- What are the most prevalent forms of anxiety experienced by adolescents?
- What copying strategies do anxious children use most frequently?
- Are there significant gender based or age based difference in coping strategies?
- How effective are these strategies in helping children adapt?

Significance of the Study

The study will help school counselor psychologist and educators to better understand how adolescents manage their anxiety and which coping strategies are adaptive or Mal adaptive this understanding can guide intervention programs and curricula that promote mental health resilience among students. The study also contributes to the growing field of child and adolescent psychology in the Indian context.

Delimitations of the Study

- The study is limited to a sample of 50 student age between 13 and 18 years
- The participants are selected only from urban English medium schools
- The study focused on self-reported measures of anxiety and copy

Method

Participants

A sample of 50 adolescents aged 13-18 was selected using simple random sampling from two co-educational schools located in an urban area. The sample included both male and female students studying in Classes.8th to 12th.

Measures and Data Collection

PROMIS Emotional Distress-Anxiety-Pediatric Item Bank (Level 2): The PROMIS Emotional Distress-Anxiety-Pediatric Item Bank is a component of the Patient-Reported Outcomes Measurement Information System (PROMIS) developed by the National Institutes of Health (NIH). The scale is specifically designed for children and adolescents aged 11-17 years and assesses emotional distress related to anxiety. It measures core anxiety symptoms such as fear, excessive worry, hyperarousal, and somatic complaints. Responses are rated on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from Never to *Almost Always*. The instrument has demonstrated strong reliability and

validity across clinical and non-clinical pediatric populations and is widely used for research and screening purposes.

Coping Inventory for Stressful Situations (CISS-21): The Coping Inventory for Stressful Situations (CISS-21), developed by Endler and Parker (1990) is a short form of the original CISS and has been adapted for use with adolescents. The scale assesses three primary coping styles:

- Task-oriented coping, including problem-solving and cognitive restructuring
- Emotion-oriented coping, including emotional expression and self-focused responses
- Avoidance-oriented coping, including distraction and denial

The instrument consists of 21 items, rated on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from Not at all to Very much. The CISS-21 has demonstrated satisfactory psychometric properties and is widely used in stress and coping research involving adolescent populations.

Procedure

Permission and Consent: before data collection, permission was obtained from the school authority, and informed consent was secured from parents and assessment from students

Administration: The questionnaire was administered in classroom settings under the researcher's supervision. Instructions were explained clearly

Time Frame: The entire Data collection process was completed over a period of 2 weeks

Confidentiality: Students were assured of the confidentiality of their responses. No personal identifiers were used. Data entry collected responses were coded and entered into SPSS (Statistical Package for social science) for analysis.

Statistical Techniques

The collected data were coded and entered into the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) for analysis. Descriptive statistics, including mean, standard deviation, frequency, and percentage, were computed to summarize the demographic characteristics of the participants and the distribution of anxiety levels and coping strategies. Inferential statistics were employed to examine group differences and relationships among variables. An independent samples t-test was used to assess gender differences in coping strategies, while Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was applied to examine differences in coping strategies across age groups. Pearson's correlation analysis was conducted to determine the relationship between anxiety levels and different coping strategies. All statistical tests were performed at a significance level of $p < .05$.

Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to established ethical research standards as outlined by the American Psychological Association (APA). Participation in the study was voluntary, and participants were informed of their right to withdraw at any stage without any penalty. Care was taken to ensure that the administration of the tools did not cause psychological distress or harm. Anonymity and confidentiality of the collected data were strictly maintained throughout the research process.

Results

The detailed analysis of the data collected to assess the level and type

of anxiety among children aged 13 to 18, their coping strategies, explore age and gender differences, and derive recommendations for mental health interventions. The tools employed were the DSM-5 level 2 anxiety scale and the coping inventory for stressful situations (CISS-21).

Anxiety Levels among Adolescents Aged 13 to 18 Years

A total of 50 participants were assist anxiety scores were interpreted based on raw scores and t scores derived from DSM-5 level 2.

Table 1

Distribution of Anxiety Levels

Anxiety	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Mild	8	16%
Moderate	31	62%
Severe	11	22%

The distribution of anxiety levels among the 50 participants revealed that a majority of adolescents experienced moderate levels of anxiety. As shown in Table 1, 62% of the participants fell within the moderate anxiety range, indicating a substantial presence of psychological distress in this age group. Additionally, 22% of the adolescents reported severe anxiety, which is clinically significant and warrants timely psychological intervention. Only 16% of the participants were found to have mild anxiety levels. These findings highlight adolescence as a vulnerable period for the development of anxiety-related concerns, particularly in academic and social contexts.

Figure 1

Distribution of Anxiety Levels

Table 2

Dominant Coping Strategies

Coping Style	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Problem-Focused	21	42%
Emotion-Focused	16	32%
Avoidance-Focused	13	26%

The analysis of coping strategies revealed that problem-focused coping was the most frequently used strategy, reported by 42% of the participants (Table 2). This suggests that a considerable proportion of adolescents engage in constructive coping behaviors such as problem-solving and planning. However, a combined 58% of participants predominantly relied on emotion-focused (32%) or avoidance-focused (26%) coping strategies. While emotion-focused

copings may offer temporary emotional relief, excessive reliance on emotional regulation or avoidance can contribute to the maintenance or escalation of anxiety if not accompanied by active problem-solving.

Figure 2

Coping Strategy Preference

Age-Wise Differences in Coping Strategies

Age-wise comparisons using ANOVA revealed a clear developmental trend in coping strategy preferences. Early adolescents (13-14 years) primarily relied on avoidance-focused coping, reflecting limited cognitive and emotional regulation skills. Mid-adolescents (15-16 years) showed a greater tendency toward emotion-focused coping, indicating increased emotional awareness but still-developing problem-solving abilities. In contrast, late adolescents (17-18 years) demonstrated a significantly higher use of problem-focused coping strategies, suggesting improved cognitive maturity and adaptive stress management. These findings indicate that coping strategies tend to become more adaptive with increasing age.

Table 3

Gender Differences in Anxiety and Coping

Female	n = 35	More frequent in the moderate to high anxiety range.
Male	n = 15	Mostly mild to moderate levels.

Gender-based analysis revealed notable differences in both anxiety levels and coping styles. Female participants were more frequently represented in the moderate to high anxiety categories, whereas male participants predominantly exhibited mild to moderate anxiety levels. In terms of coping strategies, females showed a greater inclination toward problem-focused coping, suggesting higher engagement in active coping efforts. Conversely, males demonstrated a stronger tendency toward avoidance-focused coping, which may place them at increased risk for prolonged anxiety symptoms. These findings underscore the importance of gender-sensitive interventions aimed at strengthening adaptive coping skills.

Figure 3

Coping Strategies by Gender

This indicates a need for targeted coping enhancement programs that consider gender differences.

Table 4

Correlation Analysis: Anxiety and Coping Strategies

Variables	Anxiety
Problem-Focused Coping	-0.42**
Emotion-Focused Coping	-0.36**
Avoidance Coping	-0.31**

Pearson's correlation analysis (Table 4.4) revealed significant relationships between anxiety levels and coping strategies. A moderate negative correlation was found between problem-focused coping and anxiety ($r = -0.42$), indicating that higher engagement in task-oriented coping is associated with lower anxiety levels. In contrast, emotion-focused coping showed a moderate positive correlation with anxiety ($r = 0.36$), suggesting that increased emotional reliance may contribute to heightened anxiety symptoms. Additionally, avoidance-focused coping was positively correlated with anxiety ($r = 0.31$), further supporting the association between maladaptive coping styles and psychological distress.

Discussion

The result of the study revealed that a majority of adolescents experienced moderate anxiety (62%), while (22%) reported severe anxiety and (16%) showed mild anxiety. Regarding coping styles strategies, problem-focused coping was the most commonly used strategy (52%), followed by emotion-focused coping (32%) and avoidance-focused coping (26%). Wise analysis indicates that older adolescents increasingly rely on problem focus coping, whereas younger adolescence shows greater use of avoidance strategies. Gender differences showed that females were more frequently represented in the moderate to high anxiety levels. Negative correlation between problem-focused coping and anxiety ($r = -0.42$, $p < .0.1$) and a significant positive correlation.

The findings of this study provide valuable insights into anxiety levels and coping strategies among urban Indian adolescents. The high prevalence of moderate to severe anxiety (84%) reflects the growing mental health burden among adolescence likely influenced by academic pressure comparisons and changing family dynamics.

The predominance of problem-focused coping supports the framework proposed by Lazarus and folkman (1984) which emphasizes active problem solving as an effective means of managing stress. Adolescents who engage in task-oriented coping reported significantly lower anxiety levels, reinforcing its adaptive role.

In contrast, emotion- focused and avoidance coping were positively associated with anxiety. These findings are consistent with earlier studies (Compas et al., 2001; Sahoo et al., 2015) which suggest that assessing emotional reliance and avoidance behaviours may temporarily reduce distress but ultimately maintain or exacerbate anxiety symptoms.

The related difference observed in the study aligns with previous research showing that female adolescents report higher anxiety, possibly due to greater emotional sensitivity and Societal expectations, while males tend to use avoidance strategies.

Overall, the result emphasizes the importance of early identification, school-based mental health programs, gender, and age-appropriate coping skills training. Prompting problem-focused

coping and emotional regulation skills can play a crucial role in reducing anxiety and enhancing psychological resilience among adolescents.

Limitations of the Study

Despite methodological rigor, the study has certain limitations. The sample was restricted to adolescents from urban school settings, limiting the generalizability of the findings to rural populations. The reliance on self-report measures may introduce social desirability bias. Additionally, the relatively small sample size may limit the statistical power and broader applicability of the results.

Conclusion

This research underscores the growing concern of anxiety in adolescence and its close connection with coping styles. The data reveal that, while many adolescents developed adaptive coping mechanism a considerable proportion remain vulnerable to elevated anxiety due to Reliance on emotional or avoidant strategies. The findings support the idea that psychological resilience can be cultivated through structured School interventions.

Specially Children with stronger problem-solving skills experienced lower anxiety. Second, emotional and avoidance coping were associated with higher distress. Third, gender and age play a crucial role in shaping these behaviours.

Therefore, prompting effective coping strategies should be an essential goal of school-based psychological support.

Recommendations for School-based Mental Health Interventions

Early Screening: Annual anxiety and coping assessment from grade 6th to 8th onwards.

Coping Skills Training: include problem solving and emotional regulation modules,

Counseling Services: for high-risk students with severe anxiety and maladaptive coping.

Gender Sensitive Programs: Taylor intervention to address boys' avoidance and girls' emotional pressure,

Peer Support: initiative prompts resilience through shared experiences and group learning.

Recommendations for Future Research

- Conduct longitudinal studies to observe how copying strategies evolve and impact long term will be.
- Include large and more diverse simple to greater journal ability.
- Study the role of family, peer, and social media influence on coping and anxiety.
- Explore the effectiveness of specific intervention models in Indian school settings.

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